

Appendix to Denhaerynck et al. 2026 – Temporal patterns of all-cause mortality among U.S. nursing home residents across COVID-19 vaccination strata: dataset documentation and annotated code summary

A.1 Data Sources and Structure

Dataset	Source	Unit of observation	Timespan
COVID-19 Nursing Home Data	Original source: CMS. COVID-19 Nursing Home Data. https://data.cms.gov/covid-19/covid-19-nursing-home-data (now offline) - Dataset retrieved on October, 24, 2023 Public domain material - U.S. Government Work	Facility-week	
County Socio-demographics	Simplemaps U.S. Counties Database https://simplemaps.com/data/us-counties	County	2021
County Baseline Mortality	Kirsch GitHub regression analysis	County (per month)	Jan–Dec 2020
Data Excerpts	The analytic dataset is archived at Zenodo under CC0 Public Domain Dedication (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19193433). County-level latitude values are provided under the CC BY 4.0 license and attributed to CIESIN (Columbia University, GPWv4). The percentage White population variable was obtained from the Simplemaps U.S. Counties Database (2021 edition) and is not redistributed here due to licensing restrictions.	County- and nursing home-level data are linked by county FIPS code	May 2022 – June 2023

A.2 Variable Construction Overview

Variable	Description	Column name name in original Nursing Home data
WeekEnding	Last day (MM/DD/YY) of reporting week (a reporting week is from Monday through Sunday).	Week Ending
FederalProviderNumber	The Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services Certification Number for the provider	Federal Provider Number
ProviderState	The provider's state	Provider State
County	The provider's county	County

Variable	Description	Column name name in original Nursing Home data
TotalNumberofOccupiedBeds	Number of occupied beds that week, to be transformed into $\ln(\text{Total Number of Occupied Beds})$	Total Number of Occupied Beds
ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths	Number of residents who have died in the facility or another location (total deaths) as reported by the provider	Residents Weekly All Deaths
Residentsweeklyconfirmedcovid19	Number of residents with new laboratory positive COVID-19 (confirmed) as reported by the provider	Residents Weekly Confirmed COVID-19
v_not	Weekly counts of residents with lab-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection by vaccine status as reported by the provider	Number of Residents Not Vaccinated with COVID-19 Vaccine or who Received COVID-19 Vaccine Dose 1, 13 Days or Less Before Positive Test
v_boost2	Weekly counts of residents with lab-confirmed SARS-CoV-2 infection by vaccine status as reported by the provider	Number of Residents who Received Two or More COVID-19 Vaccine Boosters, 14 Days or More Before Positive Test
v_rest	To be calculated as: $v_rest = \text{residentsweeklyconfirmedcovid19} - v_not - v_boost2$	/
ResidentsWeeklyAdmissionsCOVID19	Number of residents admitted or readmitted who were previously hospitalized and treated for COVID-19 as reported by the provider	Residents Weekly Admissions COVID-19
Perc_completed_vacc	(Number of Residents Staying in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week who Received a Completed COVID-19 Vaccination at Any Time / Number of Residents Staying in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week) * 100	Percentage of Current Residents who Received a Completed COVID-19 Vaccination at Any Time
Perc_partial_vacc	(Number of Residents Staying in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week who Received a Partial COVID-19 Vaccination at Any Time / Number of Residents Staying in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week) * 100	Percentage of Current Residents who Received a Partial COVID-19 Vaccination at Any Time
perc_staff_compl_vacc	(Number of Healthcare Personnel with a Completed Vaccination Staying in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week who Received a COVID-19 Vaccine Booster at Any Time / Number of All Healthcare	Percentage of Current Healthcare Personnel with a Completed Vaccination who Received a COVID-19 Vaccine Booster at Any Time

Variable	Description	Column name name in original Nursing Home data
	Personnel Eligible to Work in this Facility for At Least 1 Day This Week who Received a Completed COVID-19 Vaccination at Any Time) * 100	
StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19	Number of staff and facility personnel with new laboratory positive COVID-19 (confirmed) as reported by the provider	Staff Weekly Confirmed COVID-19
staff_shortage	Indicates (1=Y/0=N) if staffing shortage (overall)	Staff Shortage
month	Calender month	/
lat	The latitude of the county	/
race_white	The percentage of residents who report their race White	/
deaths_2020	County-level all death counts	/
gps	Generalized Propensity Scores (Computed by PROC MIXED residuals; see code below)	/
lag variables: lag1_<variable name>, lag2_<variable name>, ..., lagn_<variable name>	Lag 1 to n week versions of predictors	/
gps1, gps2, ..., gpsn	Generalized Propensity Scores pertaining to the respective weekly lags	/
County_FIPS	Federal Information Processing Standard unique county code	/

A.3 Software Environment

Software: SAS 9.4 (Statistical Analysis System, Cary NC)

OS: Windows 11 x64

Main procedures: PROC GLIMMIX, PROC MIXED

A.4 Modeling

Poisson regression

The formal equation of the modeling reads as:

$$\log(\mu_{it}) = \log(n_{it}) + \alpha + X_{it}\beta + u_i, u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2), Y_{it} | u_i \sim \text{Poisson}(\mu_{it})$$

Here, Y_{it} denotes deaths in facility i during week t , n_{it} the number of occupied beds (offset), X_{it} the matrix of fixed-effect predictors (including propensity scores), and $u_i \sim N(0, \sigma_u^2)$ a facility-specific random intercept, all under the assumption that $\text{Var}(Y_{it} | u_i) = \mu_{it}$.

Propensity-Score Computation

Purpose: Derive generalized propensity scores for time-varying confounder adjustment following Ertefaie and Moodie (2010, 2012). No inverse weighting; scores enter as covariates.

Method: The generalized propensity scores were calculated from Pearson's residuals [i.e. $\exp(-0.5(\text{Pearson residuals})^2)$] after first regressing the total number of COVID-positives onto all of the possible confounders that pertained to the respective time points (see figure). A linear random-intercepts regression analysis was performed for that purpose, using the natural logarithm of death counts as the outcome variable, including the natural logarithm of occupied bed-days as an offset to account for exposure, and adjusting for time-variant and -invariant confounders. The working covariance of the random effect used a Toeplitz structure with estimated parameters allowing for four weeks of serial correlation.

Code:

```
title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Concurrent';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Plain confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */
    ResidentsWeeklyAdmissionsCOVID19 lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
    perc_staff_compl_vacc lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc
lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc
    StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19
lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19
    staff_shortage lag1_staff_shortage lag2_staff_shortage lag3_staff_shortage lag4_staff_shortage
/*Previous responses*/ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
/*Previous exposure*/ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
    / outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
```

```

random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) ;
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
parms (0.002338) (0.02520) (0.005354) (0.000075) (0.2149);
run;

data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 2';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag1_staff_shortage
lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_staff_shortage
lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag3_staff_shortage
lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
/*Previous responses */ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
/*Previous Exposures */ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
/ outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) ;
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS2 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 3';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =

```

```

/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
    lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_staff_shortage
    lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag3_staff_shortage
    lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
/*Previous responses */ lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
/*Previous Exposures */ lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
    / outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

    data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS3 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 4';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */ lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
    lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag3_staff_shortage
    lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
/*Previous responses */ lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
/*Previous Exposures */ lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
    / outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

    data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS4 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

```

```

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 5';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */ lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc
lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
/ outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) ;
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS5 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 6';
proc mixed data = test;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag5_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders */ lag5_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag5_perc_staff_compl_vacc
lag5_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag5_staff_shortage
/ outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

data test;
merge test out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test (drop = pearsonresid);
set test;
GPS6 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

/*Time-reversed*/
title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality Concurrent';
proc mixed data = test_rev;

```

```

class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
  /*Plain confounders*/ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
  /*Time-varying confounders*/
  ResidentsWeeklyAdmissionsCOVID19 lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
  lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
  perc_staff_compl_vacc lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc
  lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc
  StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19
  lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19
  staff_shortage lag1_staff_shortage lag2_staff_shortage lag3_staff_shortage lag4_staff_shortage
  /*Previous responses*/ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
  lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
  /*Previous exposure*/ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
  lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
  / outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) ;
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

  data test_rev;
  merge test_rev out (keep = pearsonresid);
  data test_rev (drop = pearsonresid);
  set test_rev;
  GPS = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality T2';
proc mixed data = test_rev;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
  /*Concurrent confounders*/ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
  /*Time-varying confounders*/ lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
  lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
  lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag1_staff_shortage
  lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_staff_shortage
  lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag3_staff_shortage
  lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
  /*Previous responses */ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
  /*Previous Exposures */ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19

```

```

/ outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

data test_rev;
merge test_rev out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test_rev (drop = pearsonresid);
set test_rev;
GPS2 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality T3';
proc mixed data = test_rev;
class month federalprovidernumber providerstate time;
model l_lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 =
/*Concurrent confounders */ month l_occbeds lat race_white deaths_2020
/*Time-varying confounders*/ lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19
lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag2_staff_shortage
lag3_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag3_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag3_staff_shortage
lag4_perc_staff_compl_vacc lag4_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 lag4_staff_shortage
/*Previous responses*/ lag3_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths lag4_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths
/*Previous Exposures*/ lag3_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 lag4_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19
/ outpred=out residual ddfm=bw;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
repeated time / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) type = toep(4);
run;

data test_rev;
merge test_rev out (keep = pearsonresid);
data test_rev (drop = pearsonresid);
set test_rev;
GPS3 = (exp(-0.5*(pearsonresid**2)));
run;

```

A.5 Model Specification

```

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Concurrent';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;

```

```

model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_boost2*v_boost2 v_rest*v_rest v_not*v_not gps gps*gps / s
link=log dist = poisson offset = l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# fully vaccinated' v_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# partially vaccinated' v_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# unvaccinated' v_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' v_boost2*v_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' v_rest*v_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction unvaccinated' v_not*v_not 1 / exp cl;
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 2';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 lag1_rest*lag1_rest
lag1_not*lag1_not gps2 gps2*gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps gps*gps /s link=log dist = poisson offset =
l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate) ;
estimate '1w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged unvaccinated' lag1_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' lag1_rest*lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction unvaccinated' lag1_not*lag1_not 1 / exp cl;
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 3';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag2_rest lag2_boost2 lag2_not lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2 lag2_rest*lag2_rest
/*lag2_not*lag2_not*/ gps3*gps3 gps3
lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_not*lag1_not gps2*gps2 gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps*gps gps / s link=log dist = poisson offset =
l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '2w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag2_boost2 1 / exp cl;

```

```

estimate '2w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag2_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '2w Lagged unvaccinated' lag2_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' lag2_rest*lag2_rest 1 / exp cl;
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 4';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag3_rest lag3_boost2 lag3_not lag3_boost2*lag3_boost2 /*lag3_rest*lag3_rest
lag3_not*lag3_not*/ gps4*gps4 gps4
lag2_rest lag2_boost2 lag2_not lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2 lag2_rest*lag2_rest /*lag2_not*lag2_not*/ gps3 gps3*gps3
lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_not*lag1_not gps2 gps2*gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps gps*gps / s link=log dist = poisson offset =
l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '3w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag3_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '3w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag3_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '3w Lagged unvaccinated' lag3_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag3_boost2*lag3_boost2 1 / exp cl;
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 5';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths =
lag4_rest lag4_boost2 lag4_not lag4_boost2*lag4_boost2 /*lag4_rest*lag4_rest lag4_not*lag4_not*/ gps5*gps5 gps5
lag3_rest lag3_boost2 lag3_not lag3_boost2*lag3_boost2 /*lag3_rest*lag3_rest lag3_not*lag3_not*/ gps4*gps4 gps4
lag2_rest lag2_boost2 lag2_not lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2 lag2_rest*lag2_rest /*lag2_not*lag2_not*/ gps3*gps3 gps3
lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_not*lag1_not gps2*gps2 gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps*gps gps / s link=log dist = poisson offset =
l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '4w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag4_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '4w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag4_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '4w Lagged unvaccinated' lag4_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag4_boost2*lag4_boost2 1 / exp cl;

```

```

run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent --> Mortality Week 6';
proc glimmix data = test method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths =
lag5_rest lag5_boost2 lag5_not lag5_boost2*lag5_boost2 /*lag5_rest*lag5_rest lag5_not*lag5_not*/ gps6*gps6 gps6
lag4_rest lag4_boost2 lag4_not lag4_boost2*lag4_boost2 /*lag4_rest*lag4_rest lag4_not*lag4_not*/ gps5*gps5 gps5
lag3_rest lag3_boost2 lag3_not lag3_boost2*lag3_boost2 /*lag3_rest*lag3_rest lag3_not*lag3_not*/ gps4*gps4 gps4
lag2_rest lag2_boost2 lag2_not lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2 lag2_rest*lag2_rest /*lag2_not*lag2_not*/ gps3*gps3 gps3
lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_not*lag1_not gps2*gps2 gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps*gps gps / s link=log dist = poisson offset
= l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '5w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag5_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '5w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag5_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '5w Lagged unvaccinated' lag5_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag5_boost2*lag5_boost2 1 / exp cl;
run;

/*Time-reversed*/

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality Concurrent';
proc glimmix data = test_rev method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_boost2*v_boost2 v_rest*v_rest v_not*v_not gps gps*gps / s
link=log dist = poisson offset = l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# fully vaccinated' v_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# partially vaccinated' v_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '# unvaccinated' v_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' v_boost2*v_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' v_rest*v_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction unvaccinated' v_not*v_not 1 / exp cl;
run;

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality Week 2';

```

```

proc glimmix data = test_rev method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2
/*lag1_not*lag1_not*/ gps2 gps2*gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps gps*gps
/ s link=log dist = poisson offset = l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged unvaccinated' lag1_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' lag1_rest*lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
run;

```

```

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality Week 2 (sensitivity analysis not nested)';

```

```

proc glimmix data = test_rev method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2
/*lag1_not*lag1_not*/ gps2 gps2*gps2
/ s link=log dist = poisson offset = l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);
estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '1w Lagged unvaccinated' lag1_not 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction fully vaccinated' lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate 'Interaction partially vaccinated' lag1_rest*lag1_rest 1 / exp cl;
run;

```

```

title 'Positive test Concurrent <-- Mortality Week 3';

```

```

proc glimmix data = test_rev method = quad (initpl=5) empirical;
class federalprovidernumber providerstate;
model ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag2_rest lag2_boost2 lag2_not /*lag2_rest*lag2_rest lag2_boost2*lag2_boost2
lag2_not*lag2_not*/ gps3*gps3 gps3
lag1_rest lag1_boost2 lag1_not lag1_rest*lag1_rest lag1_boost2*lag1_boost2 /*lag1_not*lag1_not*/ gps2*gps2 gps2
v_rest v_boost2 v_not v_rest*v_rest v_boost2*v_boost2 v_not*v_not gps*gps gps / s link=log dist = poisson offset =
l_occbeds;
random intercept / subject = federalprovidernumber(providerstate);

```

```

estimate 'Intercept' intercept 1 / exp cl;
estimate '2w Lagged # fully vaccinated' lag2_boost2 1 / exp cl;
estimate '2w Lagged # partially vaccinated' lag2_rest 1 / exp cl;
estimate '2w Lagged unvaccinated' lag2_not 1 / exp cl;
run;

```

A.6 Lagging procedure

```

proc sort data = NursingHomeData;
by federalprovidernumber weekending;

data lags ;
set NursingHomeData;
weekdiff = weekending - week2;
temp = lag1(weekdiff);
if weekdiff = 7 and temp > 7 then first_seq = 1; /*First observation in a series of sequential weekly data*/

data lags;
set lags (where = (weekdiff = 7));
lag1_diff12_10 = lag1(diff12_10);
lag1_Perc_completed_vacc_10 = lag1(Perc_completed_vacc_10);
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 = lag1(ResidentsWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19);
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 = lag1(ResidentsWeeklyAdmissionsCOVID19);
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag1(ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths);
lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 = lag1(StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19);
lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc = lag1(perc_staff_compl_vacc);
lag1_Staff_Shortage = lag1(Staff_Shortage);
lag1_rest = lag1(v_rest);
lag1_boost2 = lag1(v_boost2);
lag1_not = lag1(v_not);

data lags;
retain weekending federalprovidernumber first_seq;
set lags;
by federalprovidernumber;
if first.federalprovidernumber then do;
    first_seq = 1;
    lag1_diff12_10 = .;
    lag1_Perc_completed_vacc_10 = .;

```

```
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 = .;
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 = .;
lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = .;
lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 = .;
lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc = .;
lag1_Staff_Shortage = .;
lag1_rest = .;
lag1_boost2 = .;
lag1_not = .;
end;
```

```
run;
```

```
data lags;
```

```
set lags;
```

```
lag2_diff12_10 = lag1(lag1_diff12_10);
lag2_Perc_completed_vacc_10 = lag1(lag1_Perc_completed_vacc_10);
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 = lag1(lag1_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19);
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 = lag1(lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19);
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = lag1(lag1_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths);
lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 = lag1(lag1_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19);
lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc = lag1(lag1_perc_staff_compl_vacc);
lag2_Staff_Shortage = lag1(lag1_Staff_Shortage);
lag2_rest = lag1(lag1_rest);
lag2_boost2 = lag1(lag1_boost2);
lag2_not = lag1(lag1_not);
```

```
data lags;
```

```
set lags;
```

```
by federalprovidernumber;
```

```
if first.federalprovidernumber then do;
```

```
lag2_diff12_10 = .;
lag2_Perc_completed_vacc_10 = .;
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyConfCOV19 = .;
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAdmCOV19 = .;
lag2_ResidentsWeeklyAllDeaths = .;
lag2_StaffWeeklyConfirmedCOVID19 = .;
lag2_perc_staff_compl_vacc = .;
lag2_Staff_Shortage = .;
lag2_rest = .;
```

```
    lag2_boost2 = .;
    lag2_not = .;
end;
run;

/*Reversed lags*/
proc sort data = NursingHomeData;
by federalprovidernumber descending weekending;

data rlags ;
set NursingHomeData;
...
```

A.7 Reproducibility Note

Code fragments above illustrate full model logic, parameterization, and variable transformations and can be used to replicate the analyses after merging the mentioned datasets. This work is an independent scientific analysis. The authors make no medical, diagnostic, or policy recommendations; the results are presented solely for scholarly discussion.